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The CMS Tracker Performance in Run 3

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Abstract

The CMS Tracker is the innermost part of the CMS detector. Due to its proximity to the beam-pipe, degradation due to radiation is expected, and its effects are monitored closely. Upgrades to the detector during long-shutdown along with routine calibrations and maintenance during data-taking periods help to mitigate the radiation effects. Throughout 2022 and 2023 data-taking periods, the CMS Tracker has been acquiring excellent data with very high hit-efficiency and resolution despite the demanding conditions of Run 3.

1 Introduction

The CMS Tracker is the innermost part of the CMS detector, comprised of the Pixel (BPix, FPix) and the Strip (TIB, TID, TOB, TEC) sub-detectors, sketched in Figure 1. The Tracker consists of 14 barrel layers and 15 disks in the forward regions, with a total of 1,856 Pixel modules and 15,148 Strip modules, all made out of silicon. The Tracker allows for the tracking of charged particles with high precision, and it is essential in particle identification, heavy-flavour tagging, trigger decisions, and vertex reconstruction.

Figure 1: Sketch of one quarter of the CMS Tracker in r-z view

The Tracker's proximity to the beam-pipe places it in a particularly harsh radiation environment. Degradation of performance due to radiation is expected and measures are taken to mitigate its effects. Aside from continuous mitigation efforts during data-taking period, the CMS Tracker also underwent upgrades and maintenance during LS2 to prepare for Run 3's data taking period.

The article is organized as follows: improvements to the detector since Run 2 is outlined, both in hardware and in tracker alignment procedure. Then a few examples of visible degradation of performance due to radiation is illustrated, along with the measures that were taken to recover the performance. Finally, the overall performance of the CMS Tracker during Run 3 is presented.

2 Improvements since Run 2

To prepare for Run 3's expected 250 fb^{-1} of integrated luminosity, various upgrades and maintenance were performed to enhance the Tracker's data-taking capabilities.

The Pixel detector received a brand-new BPix layer 1, installed in 2021. The new BPix layer 1 is able to be operated at up to 800 V compared to 600 V previously during Run 2. It also features enhanced front-end ASICs to improve efficiency and increase resistance against single-event upsets [1].

Precise measurements of the position and orientation of each silicon sensors are essential to utilize their excellent resolution in tracking charged particle trajectories. To this end, a more granular Online alignment procedure integrated in the Prompt Calibration Loop (PCL) was developed. The new high granularity PCL (HG-PCL) employs in the order of 5,000 parameters in contrast to the 36 parameters in the old low granularity PCL (LG-PCL).

3 Coping with radiation

Being the innermost part of the CMS detector, the CMS Tracker is subject to a high degree of radiation. The first layer of BPix is located a mere 3 cm away from the beam-pipe. Degradation of performance due to radiation is expected, and is visible in properties such as hit efficiency (for Pixel) and signal-to-noise ratio (for Strips) [2][3]. Effects of radiation are closely monitored and continuous effort is done to mitigate these effects to maintain the performance of the Tracker.

Routine bias voltage scans are performed for the Pixel and the operational bias voltage is increased as needed.

Likewise, various measures are done to the Strips. The temperatures and bias voltage of the Strips are adjusted to mitigate leakage currents in the silicon modules. During no-beam periods, beneficial annealing also help improve performance. The overall trend of degradation in hit efficiency and signal-to-noise ratio is shown in Figure 2.

(a) BPix Hit Efficiency vs delivered integrated luminosity during Run 3

(b) Signal-to-noise ratio of the Strips detector measured in pp collision in Run 2 and Run 3

Figure 2: Degradation on hit efficiency for Pixel and signal-to-noise ratio for Strips is visible as more luminosity is recorded. Increase of bias voltage for Pixel and beneficial annealing show to mitigate the degradation

4 Performance in Run 3

Throughout the 2022 and 2023 data-taking periods, both the Pixel and Strips have been taking excellent data at high trigger rates and high pile-up conditions up to 65 pile-up. The Tracker participated in all proton-proton data-taking runs, amounting to 42 fb^{-1} of data in 2022 and around 20 fb^{-1} in 2023 so far. Both the Strips and the Pixel have very high hit efficiency with more than 95% and 98% of active detector fractions respectively, shown in Figure 3.

(a) Hit efficiency of all Pixel parts as a function of instantaneous luminosity

(b) Active detector fraction of the Strips

Figure 3: Hit efficiency of the Pixel and active detector fraction of the Strips. Both show that the Tracker is in good condition and able to take quality data

Aside from active effort of radiation mitigation and hardware-based upgrades and mainte-

nance of the detector, the alignment on the Tracker plays an important role in assuring the good performance of the detector. Accurate determination of the position and orientation of the silicon sensors is crucial to effectively harness their exceptional resolution in tracing trajectories of charged particles. The increasing offset of the BPix hit residuals is recovered by increasing the sensor bias voltage and kept stable by the improved online alignment procedure HG-PCL. The HG-PCL is able to match the Offline alignment procedure in terms of keeping the offset stable [4], as shown in blue (HG-PCL) and red (Offline) in Figure 4.

(a) The root mean square (RMS) of the average impact parameter in the transverse (d_{xy}) plane in bins of the track azimuthal angle for the Pixel barrel modules

(b) BPIX residual offset for Layer 1

Figure 4: The increase in the offset up to 10.9 fb^{-1} caused by radiation damage, is recovered by the increase in sensor HV. At the same time, the alignment the HG-PCL was employed, keeping the offset more stable

5 Conclusion

Thanks to improvements made since Run 2 and continuous efforts in mitigating radiation effects, the CMS Tracker has been successfully acquiring valuable data. The CMS Tracker showed excellent tracking performance with very high hit efficiency and resolution despite the demanding conditions of Run 3, including high trigger rate and high pile-up conditions.

References

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